

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF ACYCLOVIR GEL AS NOVEL DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEMS FOR TOPICAL ANTIVIRAL APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

Background: Oral herpes is a common, recurrent condition marked by painful mucosal lesions and risk of secondary bacterial infections. Conventional topical treatments suffer from poor mucosal retention, low drug penetration, and limited patient compliance. Gels, combining the hydrophilic properties of gels with the biphasic structure of emulsions, offer enhanced solubility, stability, controlled release, and mucosal penetration. Additionally, Gels further offer ease of application, high spreadability, and good patient acceptability. Clove oil, a natural analgesic, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial agent, also improves taste, promoting better compliance. **Methods:** Eleven formulations of oral gels were developed using Carbopol 974, Xanthan Gum, and HPMC as gelling agents. Methylparaben and propylparaben served as preservatives, while propylene glycol, glycerin, sucralose, triethanolamine, and tween were included as excipients for stability and patient-friendly characteristics. Strawberry flavor was also used in gel

formulation to enhance sensory appeal. Acyclovir (antiviral), and clove oil as a multifunctional additive. Formulations were evaluated for physicochemical properties, viscosity, spreadability, mucoadhesive strength, drug content, swelling index, microbial contamination, and storage stability. A mucosal irritation test was also performed to assess safety and tolerability of the formulations upon application. **Results:** Gel formulation F5

exhibited optimal viscosity, spreadability, and mucoadhesive strength among the gel group and was flavored with strawberry for enhanced acceptability. Drug content was consistently high: Acyclovir was 99.5% for F5 (Acyclovir). Microbial testing confirmed the sterility of key formulations (F5, F10, and F11), and all maintained physical and chemical stability over time. Sensory evaluation revealed improved taste and patient acceptability in clove oil and flavored formulations. **Conclusion:** The optimized oralgel formulation, containing Acyclovir, and clove oil, represents a promising and effective approach for managing oral herpes. It offers antiviral activity, enhanced muco-adhesion, and improved sensory qualities, including taste and texture. The inclusion of a tri-polymer base significantly contributes to the rheological performance and stability of the formulation. These attributes support better patient comfort, compliance, and therapeutic outcomes while minimizing systemic side effects and irritation common in oral drug delivery. It was concluded that the best gel Formulation F5 was found to be optimal viscosity, spreadability, and mucoadhesive strength among the Acyclovir gel formulations NDDS and was flavored with strawberry for enhanced acceptability. Formulation scientist from his experience and knowledge have to significantly in the preformulation study stage and is an important factor in the NDDS (Novel Drug Delivery Systems) product development process.

KEYWORDS: Acyclovir, Antiviral, NDDS, Formulation, Excipients, Development, Gel.

INTRODUCTION

Background on Herpes Simplex Virus Infection^[1-8]

Herpesviruses are a family of DNA viruses found commonly in humans and animals. Nearly 100 herpesviruses have been at least partially characterized, and most animal species have been shown to be infected by at least one member of the family. The name, derived from the Greek herein, to creep, refers to the characteristic lesions caused by two common human herpesviruses: fever blisters caused by herpes simplex and varicella and shingles induced by herpes zoster. The known herpesviruses have a common virion. architecture and four significant biological properties: They encode a large variety of enzymes involved in nucleic acid metabolism, DNA synthesis and protein processing, synthesis of viral DNA and assembly of the capsid occurs in the nucleus of infected cells, the production of infectious viral progeny is usually accompanied by destruction of the infected cell and herpesviruses can remain latent and persist for life in their natural hosts.

Latent infection occurs in specific sets of cells that differ from one virus to another. The latent viral genomes usually take the form of circular episomes, and only a small subset of viral genes is expressed. Herpes simplex virus causes a wide variety of clinical manifestations. The clinical manifestation depends on: a) The age of patient b) Immune status of the host c) Previous immunity of the patient to autologous or heterologous viruses, d) antigenic type of the virus, and e) anatomical site of involvement. Typically, HSV-1 is associated with orofacial infections (Cold sores) and encephalitis, while HSV-2 predominantly causes genital and neonatal infections. Primary infection with either virus is typically associated with systemic signs, prolonged duration, increased severity of illness and more complications.

Treatment of Herpes Simplex Virus Infection^[10-16]

Although there is currently no vaccine or permanent cure for herpes simplex virus (HSV) infections, several pharmacological interventions are available to manage symptoms, reduce transmission, and suppress recurrence. Daily administration of antiviral medications such as Acyclovir, valacyclovir, or famciclovir has been shown to lessen the frequency and severity of symptomatic episodes and reduce viral shedding.

Acyclovir is a guanosine antiviral drug and is one of the antiviral drugs most commonly used for treatment of herpes simplex virus infection, as well as herpes zoster and varicella zoster (chickenpox).

Acyclovir: it is a synthetic acyclic purine nucleotide analog, which is most commonly used to treat HSV infection. Acyclovir is useful: To diminish shedding of viruses, to decrease rate of clinical recurrences and to suppress recurrent genital infections.

Oral therapy with Acyclovir is usually recommended for primary orolabial and genital HSV infections, which are non-life-threatening. Intravenous Acyclovir is recommended for life-threatening and serious HSV infection, such as encephalitis, infections in immunocompromised patients, and occasional severe orolabial or genital cases. Other antiviral agents, including famciclovir and valacyclovir, are effective in reducing both the transmission risk and the intensity of recurrent outbreaks. These medications are essential components of HSV management, especially in patients with frequent recurrences or severe disease. Supportive treatments, including analgesics such as paracetamol and topical anesthetics like lidocaine, can alleviate pain and discomfort associated with active lesions.

Pharmaceutical Research Paths^[17-84]

Pharmaceutical research is characterized by having both a natural source and synthetic source for primary active raw materials and excipients, each source is mainly prepared to the effectiveness and safety of the drug.

The development of pharmaceutical dosage forms is the basis for delivering the drug to the body. The development of drug delivery systems makes the drug the fastest to arrive, most effective, accurate, and in fast time. Some systems were need to prolong the effect, so they operate with controlled delay system.

All of this development through the various methods of administrating medicine to the body requires developing the medicine, starting from natural and synthetic sources of raw materials for the active ingredients and excipients that are used in formulating medicines in their various dosage forms. The research related to this path is research in drug design or drug extraction, preformulation studies, formulations, evaluation research and stability studies. Clinical studies are important in the development of pharmaceutical dosage forms, and pharmacovigilance follow-up services the safety of medicines. Studying Pharmacoeconomics saves the cost of drug manufacturing, industrial pharmaceutical research and development of production lines, which makes pharmaceutical dosage forms in continues development.

Pharmaceutical care and treatments depend mainly on prescribing medications, taking into account the most important factor, which is drug delivery systems. Research and studies on the effectiveness and use of medicines, their mechanism of action, and safety are all relevant to the manufacture of pharmaceutical dosage forms. Pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics research is considered the most important factor in developing novel drug delivery systems NDDS. The continuous development in the pharmaceutical industry is accelerating in the development of drug delivery systems that serve to improve human healthcare.

Dosage Forms and Novel Drug Delivery Systems^[86-130]

The drug is defined as a substance recognized by official pharmacopoeia / In house (IH) which, is intended for its use in the diagnosis, cure, mitigation, treatment, or prevention of disease. Rarely drug is given in its pure chemical form. To ease the drug administration by a human being, it is essential to convert it into physical form in which drug is dispensed known

as dosage form. The dosage form is a package of Active Pharmaceutical Ingredient (API) along with selective non medicinal compounds known as excipients.

Dosage forms are the means by which drug molecules are delivered to sites of action within the body. The need for dosage forms: Accurate dose, protection e.g. coated tablets, sealed ampules, protection from gastric juice, masking taste and odor, placement of drugs within body tissues, sustained release medication, controlled release medication, optimal drug action, insertion of drugs into body cavities and use of desired vehicle for insoluble drugs.

A dosage form refers to the specific physical formulation through which a medicinal substance is administered to achieve therapeutic effects. Dosage forms act as delivery systems that transport active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs) to their intended sites of action within the body, enhancing therapeutic outcomes while reducing potential adverse effects. The selection of an appropriate dosage form depends on factors such as the drug's physicochemical characteristics, the desired route of administration, the patient's clinical condition, and considerations related to age and ease of use. Pharmaceutical dosage forms are composed of two essential components:

Active Pharmaceutical Ingredient (API): The pharmacologically active compound responsible for producing the desired therapeutic effect.

Excipients: Inactive substances incorporated into the formulation to ensure stability, enhance bioavailability, improve patient acceptability, or facilitate the manufacturing process. Common excipients include colorants, sweeteners, flavoring agents, surfactants, solubilizers, antioxidants, preservatives, thickening agents, suspending agents, binders, solvents, lubricants, and lipid-based materials.

The major biopharmaceutical considerations include: Pharmacodynamic Considerations, therapeutic objective, toxic effect, adverse reactions of candidate drug molecule. Drug Consideration: Physicochemical characterization of the candidate drug molecules. Drug Product Consideration: Bioavailability of candidate drug molecule, pharmacokinetics of candidate drug molecule, desired drug dosage form, route of administration for the candidate drug molecule, and desired dose of the candidate drug molecule. Patient Consideration: Compliance and acceptability of the final drug product. Manufacturing Considerations: Cost, availability of pharmaceutical raw materials, stability and quality.

Formulation and Development

This stage involves the actual combination of candidate drug molecule with various excipients and also optimizing the concentration at which each excipient is used. The choice of excipients depends on the properties of the drug molecule and the nature of the intended drug product.

Classification of Dosage Forms

Pharmaceutical dosage forms can be classified in multiple ways, depending on their physical nature, route of administration, site of application, or intended therapeutic use and related data as shown in Tables (1 to 5).

Table 1: Dosage Form Classifications Based on Physical Form State.

1	Solid Dosage Forms	Powders, Tablets, Effervescent tablets, Capsules, Soft Gelatin Capsule (SGC), Hard Gelatin Capsule (HGC) Lozenges/Troches, Granules, Effervescent Granules, Chewable, Pills, Insufflation, Cachets, snuffs, Spansules, Hypodermic Tablets, Tablet Triturates, Dental Cones, Pastilles, Pessaries, Vaginal Rings, Transdermal Patches, Suppositories, Implants, Ocular Inserts, Film coated tablet, Orodispersible Tablets, Enteric-Coated Tablets, Dispensing Tablets, Tablet Triturates, Lollipops, Chewing Gum.
2	Semi Solid Dosage Forms	Creams, Ointments, Pastes, Gels, Poultices, Suppositories, Hair colors, Shampoos, Lipsticks, Avaleha.
3	Liquid Dosage Forms	Syrups, Mixtures, Linctuses, Elixirs, Gargles, Mouthwashes, Lotions, Oral Drops, Nasal Drops, Ear Drops, Suspensions, Emulsions, Eye Washes, Liniments, Enemas, Irrigations, Draughts, Eye Drops, Douches, Drops, Tinctures, Spirits, Injections, Collodion, Paints, Throat Paints, Oxymels, Aromatic Waters. Extracts, Inhalants.
4	Gaseous Dosage Forms	Pressurized dispensers, Inhalers, Aerosols, Nebulizers, Sprays, Metered Dose Inhalers (MDIs), Dry Powder Inhalers (DPIs).
5	Special Drug Delivery System	Ocular Inserts, Progestaserts, Intra –Uterine, Liposomes, Prodrugs, Transdermal Patches.

Table 2: Dosage Form Classifications Based on Route of Administration.

1	Oral Dosage Forms	Powders, Granules, Tablets, Capsules, Suspension, Gels, Pills, Elixirs, Syrups, Emulsion.
2	Parenteral Dosage Forms	Solutions, Suspensions, Emulsions.
3	Trans dermal Dosage Forms	Ointments, Powders, Creams, Lotions, Pastes.
4	Intra ocular Dosage Forms	Solutions, Suspension, Ointments, Gels.
5	Conjunctival Dosage Forms	Ointments
6	Vaginal Dosage Forms	Solutions, Tablets, Ointments, Creams, Suppositories, Douches.

7	Sublingual Dosage Forms	Tablets, Lozenges.
8	Intra-Nasal Dosage Forms	Solutions, Sprays, Inhalations, Gels.
9	Rectal Dosage Forms	Ointments, Suppositories, Enemas.
10	Pulmonary Dosage Forms	Aerosols
11	Urethral Dosage Forms	Suppositories.
12	Intra-Otic Dosage Forms	Solutions, Suspension, Douches, Ear Powders.

Table 3: Dosage Form Classifications Based on Site of Application.

1	Skin	Powders, Emulsion, Gels, Ointments, Creams, Pastes, Lotion, Suspension, Solutions, Shampoos, Lipsticks, Liniments, Douches.
2	Eye	Ointments, Gels, Eye Drops, Eye Wash, Eye Lotion, Eye Packs, Contact Lenses.
3	Tooth	Powders, Pastes, Spray, Dental cone, Dentrifices.
4	Hand	Powder, Emulsion, Gels, Suspension, Ointments, Creams, Paste, Lotions.
5	Foot	Powder, Emulsions, Gels, Ointments, Creams, Lotions.
6	Hair	Gels, Creams, Hair serums, Hair oils, Hair Sprays, Hair colours.
7	Nose	Aerosols, Insufflations, Snuffs, Gels.
8	Ear	Ear Drops, Douches, Ear Powders.
9	Vaginal	Solutions, Tablets, Ointments, Creams, Suppositories, Douches.
10	Rectal	Ointments, Suppositories, Enemas.

Table 4: Dosage Form Classifications Based on Use.

Internal	Powders, Tablets, Capsules, Emulsion, Syrups, Elixirs, Gels, Pills, Suspension, Avaleha, Pessaries, Suppositories.
External	Aerosols, Ointments, Creams, Powders, Pastes, Lotions, Sprays, Inhalations, Liniments, Throat Paints, Plasters, Jellies, Aerosols, Pellets, Trans dermal Patches.

Table 5: Routes, Dosage Forms, and Uses.

Dosage Form	Route of Administration	Purpose/Use
Tablets/Capsules	Oral	Purpose/Use Convenient systemic delivery
Solutions/Suspensions	Oral/Topical	Rapid action, suitable for children
Injections/Infusions	Parenteral	Fast action, emergency use
Inhalers/Nebulizers	Inhalation	Respiratory therapy
Ointments/Creams/Gels	Topical	Local skin or mucosal treatment
Suppositories/Enemas	Rectal/Vaginal	Local/systemic when oral not possible
Transdermal Patches	Skin	Long-term controlled systemic effect
Modified/Controlled Forms	Varies	Targeted or sustained drug delivery

GELS

Gels are defined as semi-rigid systems in which the movement of the dispersing medium is restricted by an interlacing three-dimensional network of particles or solvated macromolecules of the dispersed phase.

The word “gel” is derived from “gelatin,” and both “gel” and “jelly” can be drawn back to the Latin gelu for “frost” and gel are, meaning freeze or ‘congeal.’ This origin indicates the essential idea of a liquid setting to a solid-like material that does not flow, but is elastic and retains some liquid characteristics.

Physicochemical Properties of Drug as Gel Dosage Form

The drug should have a molecular weight of less than 400 Daltons, highly acidic or alkaline drugs are not suitable for topical drug delivery, the drug should possess adequate lipophilicity, and ideal pH for drug candidates should range between 5 and 9.

Route of Drug Gel Penetration

Drug molecules come into touch with cellular waste, bacteria, and other substances on the skin's surface, which has an impact on penetration. Three routes connect the administered medication to the living tissue: Through the hair follicles, sweat ducts, and continuous stratum corneum between the appendages, in that order (hair follicles, sebaceous glands, eccrine, apocrine glands and nails).

Advantages of Gel Formulations

The gel formulation has several key benefits over conventional semisolid dose formulations: Compared to other formulations, gels are simple to manufacture, gel is a sophisticated, non-greasy composition, gels offer fantastic adhesion to the application region, gels are eco-friendly and biocompatible, and be incredibly resilient to stressful situations.

Disadvantages of Gel Formulations

Despite having a number of benefits. Gel formulations can come with certain drawbacks: Gels have a more gradual and persistent effect, the additives or gelators could irritate people, the risk of microbial or fungal assault on gel is increased by the presence of water, the formulation's solvent loss dries to gel, and in some gels, flocculation results in an unstable gel.

Ideal Properties of Topical Gel

The gel ought to be uniform and transparent, when shear or force is applied during the container's shaking, the gel should break easily, the gel should have an inert composition, the gel must not be sticky, the gel shouldn't ever contact with another component in the formulation, the gel must be reliable, and the skin or any area where the gel is placed shouldn't be irritated. Types of gels and related data as shown in Tables (6-11).

Table 6: Types of Gels.

Based on Colloidal Phases	a) Inorganic (two-phase system)	b) Organic (single-phase system)	
Based on Nature of the Solvent	a) Hydrogels (water- based)	b) Organogels (With a non-aqueous solvent)	c) Xerogels
Based on Physical Nature	a) Elastic Gels	b) Rigid Gels	
Based on their Rheological Properties	a) Plastic Gel	b) Pseudo-Plastic Gel	c) Thixotropic Gel

Table 7: Classification of Gels.

Nature			Cross-linking\Bond		Phase\ Physical Structure		Origin of Materials		Electrical Charge	
Hydrogels	Organogels	Xerogels	Physical Gels \ Reversible	Chemical Gels Irreversible	Single Phase Monophasic	Two Phase Biphasic\Magma	Natural Origin	Synthetic\ Semi- synthetic	Neutral	Ionic Anionic\Cationic
Water liquid Phase	An organic or Oil Phase	Solid gel	Elasticity	Viscoelastic	Macromolecules	Mass Thick	Biopolymers	Polymers	Polymer	Network
E.g. Carbopol Gelatin Agar	E.g. Petroleum, Pluronic Lecithin	E.g. Gelatin Acacia dry	E.g. Gelatin Starch	E.g. Carbopol Crosslink PEG hydrogels	E.g. Carbopol gels, Cellulose ethers	E.g. Aluminum Hydroxide gel	E.g. Ager, Alginate, Pectin, Chitosan	E.g. Carbomer Poloxamers Pluronic's	E.g. PEG	E.g. Carbopol, Chitosan

Table 8: Natural Gelling Agent Polymer for Pharmaceutical Formulations.

Polymer Name	Chemical Nature	Pharmaceutical Application
Alginate acid	A naturally occurring, edible polysaccharide found in brown algae is alginate acid, often known as alginate.	Stabilize oil-in-water emulsions as well as thicken and suspend a variety of pastes, creams, and gels.
Arginine	an amino acid that aids in the body's protein synthesis.	Immune system function, hormone production, wound healing, ammonia removal from the body, and cell division.
Chitosan	One of the most prevalent natural polysaccharides is chitin.	Antibacterial activity, non-toxicity, simplicity of modification, and biodegradability, chitosan is a bioactive polymer with a wide range of uses.
Carrageenan	Repeating galactose units, 3,6-anhydrogalactose (3,6-AG), and alternating (1-) and (1-4) glycosidic linkages joined by sulfated and non-sulfated sugars	Soft and Hard Gel Hand lotions, shampoos, emulsions, dressings, antacid gels, topical bases, suppository bases, contraceptive gels, and controlled-release tablets
Dextran	α -D-1,6-glucose-linked Glucan	Spheres or implants made of hydrogel
Guar gum	Guar gum can be a cost-effective alternative because of its good viscosity and spreadability.	Gelling and emulsifying agent
Gelatin	Combination of Polypeptide Chains of Glycine, Proline, and Hydroxyproline from Purified Protein Fractions	Gelling agents is gelatin. Film Formation/Rapid Dissolution
Hemicellulose	(Mannans/Xyloglucans/Xylans)/ 1,4-Linked Dglycans/Xyloglucans	Agent for Forming Film
Hyaluronic acid	N-Acetyl glucosamine, Glucuronic Acid, and Polyanionic Polysaccharide	Eye gel, prolonged drug release, intra articular injections, and artificial insemination
Hydroxyethyl Cellulose	Closure Ethers	Tablet Film Forming, Binders, Coating Agents, Emulsifying Agents, and Stabilizing Agents
Inulin	Glucofructan oligomer mixture, polysaccharide, and polymers that have been derivatized using succinic and methacrylic anhydrides	Methylated inulin hydrogels and film formers
Pectin	Anionic Polysaccharide -1, 4 Linked D-galacturonic Acid	Tablets (Directly Compressed, Sustained-Release, Gel Bead, Injection, Oral Film, Colon-Drug Delivery System, Transdermal Patch)
Sodium Alginate	D-Mannuronic acid and L-guluronic acid in homopolymers, as well as D-Mannuronic acid and L-guluronic acid connected by - or -1,4 glycosidic	Tablet binders, Tablet Disintegrants, Colloidal Preparation, Thickening, Stabilizing, Suspending, Gel

	linkages	Producing, Emulsion Stabilizing, and Biopolymer Film
Agar	Agarobiose (D galactose/Agaropectin) is also known as agarose and agaropectin.	Gelling suppositories, suspending agents, emulsifying agents, laxatives, bacterial cultures.
Albumin	Plasma protein is made up of three homologous domains and has 585 amino acids in human serum albumin (I,II,III)	Gene delivery, injection, creation of nanoparticles, and medication administration (based on peptide or protein).

Table 9: Semi-synthetic Polymers.

Polymer Name	Properties
Hydroxypropyl methylcellulose	Film development and prolonged product wear
Hydroxyethyl cellulose	Rheological control and simplicity of use
Polyacrylic-acid	Prolonged shelf life of the product
Polyamides	Extended product wear, improved product shelf life, rheological control, and simplicity of application
Cellulose – Derivatives	Solution viscosity and surface performance
Cellulose acetates	Topologies of thermoplastic films and heat resistance
Cellulose nitrates	Biodegradation, hydrolysis, and oxidation
Chitosan	Anti-inflammatory antioxidant, antifungal, and antimicrobial
Collagen	Serve as a fibroblast's compass.
Gelatin	Uses water to create thermally reversible gels
Pectin	Used as a gelling ingredient in food, especially in jams and jellies.
Liven	Animal-free components for proteins
Silk	Wholesome protein fibre
Nitrocellulose	Film development and prolonged product wear
Acrylate-copolymers	Upgraded product design

Table 10: Synthetic Polymers and Biomedical Applications.

Polymer Name	Biomedical Application
Poly(ether urethanes)	Heart valves, blood contacting equipment, coatings, and vascular grafts.
Carbopol 934	Suitable for usage in lotions and creams as a rheology modifier
Polyphosphazenes	Controlled medication distribution through implants and in tumor-bearing animals
Carbopol 940	In gel preparations, carbopol 940 is frequently employed as a gelling agent.
Carbopol 941	It is possible to create low-viscosity lotions and gels with high clarity using the carbopol 941 NF polymer.
Carbomer	Used to increase the biological availability of medicines and regulate their release.
Poly (vinyl)alcohol (PVA)	Suitable for vascular cell culture, tissue mimicry, and vascular implanting
Poly(ethylene glycol) (PEG)	Hydrogel, or as an antifouling coating on catheters
Polyurethane	Materials that are frequently utilized to make blood contacting devices like heart valves or synthetic veins and arteries

Poloxamers	Poloxamers are an advantageous option in pharmaceutical technology and the biomedical field.
Poly(caprolactone diol) (PCL)	Diol for making polyurethane
Polyvinylchloride (PVC)	Blood bags and blood tubes
Poly(carbonate) (PC)	Biodegradable polyester for containers and dialysis membranes

Table 11: Marketed Available formulations of Gels.

No.	Generic name	Uses
1	Pilocarpine hydrochloride	Used to treat glaucoma
2	Diclofenac Diethyl amine	Relives pain
3	Aluminum hydroxide	Heart burn and acid indigestion
4	Econazole nitrate	Anti-fungal
5	Becaplermin	Dermatologic
6	Benzoyl peroxide	Acne vulgaris
7	Magnesium hydroxide	Maintenance of acidity
8	Clobetasol propionate	Relief of inflammation
9	Metronidazole	Treat bacterial infection
10	Tretinoin cellulose	Acne vulgaris
11	Benzalkonium + Choline Salicylate + Lignocaine	Drugs For Aphthous Ulcers
12	Rosa damascena, Cardamom, Triphala.	The antimicrobial, antibacterial, and antifungal properties in vaginitis.
13	Hyaluronic Acid & Pro- Vit B5	Hyaluronic Acid & Pro-Vit B5
14	Methylene bis benzotriazole , Bis-Ethylhexylphenol methoxyphenyl triazine, Diethylamino hydroxy benzoyl hexyl benzoate, Ethylhexyl methoxycinnamate	Protect your skin from harmful UV radiation, which can cause sunburn, wrinkles, and skin cancer.
15	Glycolic Acid, Witch Hazel (anti-inflammation flowering plant), Mandelic Acid, Carrageenan and Zinc Gluconate	Mild exfoliation, oil control, and combating acne and pimples
16	Ethyl Alcohol 4% V/V + Silver Nitrate - 0.2% W/W	Burns, cuts, wounds
17	Clindamycin, Nicotinamide	Treats mild to moderate acne
18	Hydroxypropyl Methylcellulose	Alleviates dry eye conditions Provides temporary relief from the burning sensation due to dryness.
19	Triamcinolone acetonide	Inflammatory and allergic conditions, Mouth sores
20	Desonide	Seborrheic otitis externa (ear infection). Dermatitis, Eczema, Psoriasis
21	Methotrexate	Psoriasis
22	Timolol maleate	Reduce pressure inside the eyes
23	Lidocaine hydrochloride ophthalmic gel	Relives pain

In the present study, it was proposed to formulated Acyclovir gels of the safety, efficacy, quality and stability of a formulation are major concepts of any API development process. In

API development process, a detailed characterization of the API and other formulation components is usually carried out during the formulation with commonly different excipients using for development formulations of Acyclovir gel NDDS for topical application.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Acyclovir and all raw materials used in the formulation including active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs), excipients, and analytical reagents were obtained as a gift sample from (Global Pharma Pharmaceutical Industry Company - Yemen).

As shown in Table 12.

Table 12: List of Materials Used.

No.	Name of Materials
1	Acyclovir
2	Clove Oil
3	Carbopol
4	Xanthan Gum
5	Methylparaben
6	Propylparaben
7	Glycerin
8	Propylene Glycol
9	Tween 80
10	Sodium Lauryl Sulfate
11	Ethanol
12	Polyethylene Glycol 400
13	Polyethylene Glycol 6000
14	Sucralose
15	Flavor – Strawberry
16	Triethanolamine

Equipment

All equipment used are listed in Table 13.

Table 13: List of Instruments.

No.	Instruments
1	Chamber 40 °C
2	UV-VIS Spectrophotometer
3	Sc Chemtech Ultrasonic Bath
4	pH Meter
5	Brookfield Viscometer
6	Magnetic Stirrer
7	Electronic Balance
8	Digital Thermostatic Water Bath

Formulation and Evaluation of Acyclovir Gels^[185-181]

Optimization and Development of Gels

The gel was developed by integrating an oil-in-water emulsion into a Carbopol-based hydrogel matrix, creating a stable, mucoadhesive system for topical drug delivery. The comprehensive formulation process progressed through four critical stages: Gel base formation, active ingredient incorporation, and final system optimization, with specific variations implemented across different formulations (F1-F11), detailed composition of each formula is presented in Table 14.

Formulation of Acyclovir Gels

The hydrogel base formulation followed a meticulous polymer hydration protocol with formulation-specific variations. The standard preparation involved initially dispersing xanthan gum in glycerin to create a homogeneous, lump-free mixture, though this step was omitted in formulations F1, F2, F3, and F7. Concurrently, Carbopol 974 was hydrated in distilled water maintained at 70°C in a water bath. In formulation F11, hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC) was prepared using a hot hydration method to ensure complete dispersion and eliminate entrapped air bubbles. Specifically, approximately one-third of the purified water was heated to around 70 - 75°C, and HPMC powder was gradually added under continuous stirring to this hot water. This process allowed the polymer to disperse fully without forming lumps or foam, as HPMC does not dissolve at this temperature but forms a uniform suspension. After complete dispersion, the remaining water at room temperature (20-25°C) was added, and the mixture was stirred for about 30 minutes until a clear, bubble-free gel was obtained. The cooled HPMC solution was then incorporated into the hydrated Carbopol dispersion. These prepared components were then systematically integrated, with both the xanthan-glycerin mixture (where applicable) and HPMC dispersion (F11) being incorporated into the hydrated Carbopol solution. The complete polymer system underwent thorough mixing for 10 minutes to ensure complete hydration and bubble elimination.

Table 14: Composition (% w/w) of Acyclovir Gel Formulations.

Ingredients	Formulation Code										
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10	F11
Acyclovir	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Clove Oil	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.76	0.76	0.76
Carbopol	0.5	1	0.75	0.75	1	1	1.5	1	1	1	1
Xanthan Gum	-	-	-	0.5	0.5	1	-	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
Methylparaben	0.02	-	-	-	0.2	-	-	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2

Propyl paraben	-	-	-	-	0.02	-	-	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02
HPMC	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.2
Glycerin	5	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6
Propylene Glycol	7	10	7	7	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
Tween 80	0.2	0.2	-	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	1	1	1
Sodium lauryl sulfate	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Ethanol	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Sucralose	-	-	-	-	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.04	-	0.04	0.075
Strawberry flavor	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	-	-	-
TEA	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.75	1	1	1	1	1.5	1.5	1.5
Purified Water	Q.s	Q.s	Q.s	Q.s	Q.s	Q.s	Q.s	Q.s	Q.s	Q.s	Q.s

HPMC: Hydroxypropyl methylcellulose; **TEA:** Triethanolamine.

Evaluation of Acyclovir Gels

Characterization of Acyclovir Gels

Macroscopic Evaluation of Formulations

The physical appearance of the Acyclovir gel was thoroughly evaluated using various organoleptic properties, including visual observation and sensory perception. The general appearance plays a significant role in consumer acceptance, as it reflects the overall elegance, quality, and uniformity of the formulation.

Physical Appearance

The Assessment Focused on the Following Aspects

Evaluate color, homogeneity, and odor.

Color

The formulation was visually inspected to ensure it exhibited a consistent and uniform color throughout the formulation. Any discoloration or uneven shading could indicate instability or improper mixing of components.

Odor

The formulation was checked for any undesirable or strong odor. A pleasant or neutral scent is important to enhance patient compliance, especially for topical applications. The absence of any foul or medicinal odor was confirmed.

Homogeneity

The formulation was examined for uniformity in texture and composition. A homogeneous formulation should not contain any lumps, grittiness, or particulate matter, and should have a smooth, consistent feel when applied to the skin.

Phase Separation

The formulation was checked for any signs of phase separation, such as the separation of oil and aqueous layers. A stable gel should appear as a single, well-blended phase with no visible separation over time.

pH Determination Test

The pH of the oral gel formulations was measured to verify compliance with the physiological pH range of the oral cavity (typically 5.5-7.6), thus reducing potential irritancy. For each formulation, a 0.5 g sample was homogenized in 50 mL of purified water. The mixture was first vortexed for 2 minutes followed by 2 minutes of sonication to achieve complete dispersion of gel components in the aqueous medium. The pH of the resulting homogeneous mixture was then measured in triplicate using a calibrated pH meter, and the mean values were recorded.

Viscosity Test

Measure viscosity using a viscometer to ensure it meets product requirements for topical application.

Stability Studies

A stability study was conducted to evaluate the physical and chemical stability of the optimized formulations under accelerated conditions. The formulations were stored for 3 months in an accelerated stability chamber at $40^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $75\% \pm 5\%$ relative humidity. This study aimed to ensure that the formulations maintained their intended physical and chemical characteristics throughout the testing period without undergoing undesirable changes. The evaluation focused on monitoring key physical parameters such as changes in color, odor, clarity, phase separation, and overall appearance of the formulation.

Mucoadhesive Evaluation

Mucoadhesive strength of formulations was evaluated using two simple methods. In the first, a simulated mucosal membrane was placed between two glass slides. Equal amounts of each formulation were applied, and the upper slide was pressed gently for one minute. Adhesion was assessed by the resistance felt during vertical separation.

In the second method, a fixed amount of each formulation was placed on membrane-covered glass slides. The slides were then inclined at a 45° angle, and distilled water was gradually

dropped onto the samples to simulate saliva. The distance each formulation slid from its original position was measured to estimate mucoadhesive retention.

Spreadability Test

A fixed quantity of each test formulation was uniformly placed on a clean glass slide; a second glass slide was carefully placed on top to sandwich the formulation between the two slides. A standardized weight (50 g) was placed on the upper slide for a fixed duration (1 minute) to ensure even distribution and adhesion of the formulation. The weight was removed, and the time taken for the upper slide to detach completely from the lower slide due to the formulation's viscous flow was recorded in seconds (s). Good spreadability ensures uniform application over the skin and oral mucosa enhances patient compliance, and supports effective drug penetration.

Rheological Study

The viscosity of the developed formulations was determined using a viscometer apparatus. Measurements were performed using spindle sizes 93 and at 120 rotational speeds (rpm). A sample of the formulation was placed into a beaker, and the spindle was immersed in the sample. Viscosity readings were then recorded to assess the rheological behavior of the formulations.

Microbiological Contamination Testing

To ensure the microbiological safety of the prepared gel formulations, samples with optimal physical and sensory properties were submitted to a certified local laboratory for evaluation. The testing focused on detecting any microbial contamination that could affect product stability or safety. The presence or absence of viable microorganisms was assessed, and the formulations were classified accordingly as either passing or failing based on standard microbiological criteria.

Drug Content Determination Test

The drug content is determined by UV spectroscopic analysis. The equation used is:
Drug content = (Concentration × Dilution factor × Volume taken) × Conversion factor.

The concentration of Acyclovir in the formulation was quantified using UV-Visible Acyclovir, adhering to the USP acceptance range for topical formulations. A stock solution was prepared by accurately weighing 10 mg of Acyclovir (0.5 mL), was pipetted out. It was

suitably diluted with 0.1 N NaOH solution and the absorbance of this mixture was measured at 255 nm. The drug content was calculated against the absorbance of control ACV solution of the same concentration at 255 nm.

Swelling Index Test

To determine the swelling index of prepared topical gel, 1gm of gel is taken on porous aluminum foil and then placed separately in a 50 ml beaker containing 10 ml 0.1 N NaOH. Then samples were removed from beakers at different time intervals and put it on dry place for some time after it reweighed. Swelling index is calculated as follows:

$$\text{Swelling Index (SW)\%} = (W_t - W_0) / W_0 \times 100$$

Where, (SW) % = Equilibrium percent swelling, W_t = Weight of swollen gel after time t , W_0 = Original weight of gel at zero time.

Skin and Oral Mucosa Irritant Test

To assess the local tolerance and safety of the formulated Acyclovir oral gel (containing clove oil), standardized irritation testing was performed on healthy adult volunteers. Specific quantity of each formulation was topically administered to three distinct anatomical sites: (1) perioral skin, (2) labial mucosa (inner lip surface), and (3) buccal mucosa (cheek lining). All application sites were subsequently evaluated at predetermined intervals for potential irritant reactions, including erythema, edema, pruritus, burning sensation, or any other adverse local effects.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Evaluation of Formulations

Macroscopic Evaluation of Formulations

All gel formulations (F1-F8) exhibited uniform white coloration and characteristic strawberry odor when evaluated 24 hours post-preparation. In contrast, gel formulations displayed uniform off-white coloration with a distinct clove odor at the same evaluation time point. All formulations showed homogeneous distribution without visible aggregates or phase separation. When comparing all formulations: F1-F4 and F7 failed to meet the required mucoadhesive standards. F1-F4 displayed markedly poor structural integrity, characterized by watery consistency, insufficient cohesion, and presence of foam and air bubbles.

F7 demonstrated good cohesion but exhibited weak bio-adhesion properties. Notably, formulations F5, F10, and F11 demonstrated optimal physicochemical characteristics,

including: Ideal equilibrium between gel cohesion and bio-adhesion, with smooth, glossy texture free from particulate matter.

pH Determination Test

All formulations demonstrated physiologically acceptable pH values ranging from 5.5 to 6.8 (Table 15), with the exception of formulations F2, F3, and F6 which exhibited slightly acidic properties.

Table 15: Mean pH Values of the Gel Formulations.

Formulation Code	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10	F11
Mean pH Value	6.6	5.36	4.52	5.5	6.7	5.1	6.39	6.34	6.5	6.8	6.8

Swelling Index Test

The results of selected formulations as shown in Table 16.

Table 16: Swelling Index Results of the Optimized Formulations.

Formulation Code	Time (Min)	Initial Weight	Final Weight	Swelling Index%
F5	0	1.5	1.5	58%
	5	1.5	1.9	
	10	1.5	2.19	
	15	1.5	2.58	
	20	1.5	2.82	
F10	0	1.5	1.5	60%
	5	1.5	1.7	
	10	1.5	2	
	15	1.5	2.86	
	20	1.5	3.05	
F11	0	1.5	1.5	97.5%
	5	1.5	2.22	
	10	1.5	3	
	15	1.5	3.2	
	20	1.5	3.43	

Rheological Study

The rheological properties of the Acyclovir gel formulations (F1–F11) were evaluated by measuring their viscosities at 25°C using a viscometer with spindle 93 at 120 rpm. The viscosity values, presented as mean ± standard deviation of triplicate measurements, as shown in Table 17.

Viscosity measurements revealed significant variation among the formulations. Formulation F1 exhibited the lowest viscosity at 913.9 ± 74.7 cP, while formulation F6 demonstrated the highest viscosity at $20,883.3 \pm 425.2$ cP. Others exhibited intermediate viscosities were

observed in formulations. The low standard deviations indicate consistent and reproducible measurements across all formulations.

Table 17: Viscosity Measurements Results of Gel Formulations (F1–F11).

Formulation Code	Viscosity (cP) Mean \pm SD
F1	913.9 \pm 74.7
F2	17,500 \pm 180.3
F3	13,883.3 \pm 288.6
F4	15,483.3 \pm 236.3
F5	18,443.3 \pm 134.3
F6	20,883.3 \pm 425.2
F7	19,200 \pm 180.3
F8	14,096.7 \pm 965
F9	13,640 \pm 1268.5
F10	16,293 \pm 165
F11	14,380 \pm 838.6

Skin and Oral Mucosa Irritant Test

The prepared gel formulations were topically administered to the perioral skin, labial mucosa, and buccal mucosa of 20 healthy volunteers.

In two volunteers with known skin sensitivity, mild allergic reactions (grade 1 erythema) were transiently observed within the initial 40 seconds of application of the gel. These reactions resolved spontaneously without intervention and did not recur during subsequent monitoring periods. All other participants exhibited excellent tolerance to both formulations with no irritation.

Spreadability Test

Spreadability of all formulations was measured using the slide-separation method under a 50 g load. The mucoadhesive gels (F1–F8) exhibited a wide range of detachment rates (Table 18), with values spanning from 0.174 to 2.34 mm/s, whereas the gels (F9–F11) were generally more cohesive, yielding lower spreadability values between 0.124 and 0.213 mm/s. These differences reflect the balance between ease of application and formulation consistency essential for mucosal delivery.

Among the mucoadhesive gels, F5 demonstrated the most desirable profile, with a spreadability of 0.174 mm/s, combining sufficient flow for uniform coating and adequate viscosity to minimize rapid runoff. In the gel series, F10 (0.124 mm/s) and F11 (0.140 mm/s)

provided the optimal compromise between spreadability and structural integrity, suggesting enhanced residence time on oral mucosa without sacrificing patient-friendly application.

Table 18: Spreadability Measurements Results of Gel Formulations (F1–F11).

Formulation Code	Spreadability (mm\sec)
F1	2.34
F2	0.815
F3	1.66
F4	0.232
F5	0.174
F6	0.355
F7	0.360
F8	0.347
F9	0.213
F10	0.124
F11	0.140

Mucoadhesive Evaluation

The mucoadhesive strength was evaluated using both the slide separation method and the inclined slide method. Formulation F5 showed stronger adhesion than Formulation F4 in both tests, indicating improved mucoadhesive properties.

Formulations F10 and F11 both demonstrated strong adhesion in the two test methods. In the slide separation method, F11 showed slightly higher resistance than F10, suggesting stronger bonding to the membrane. In the inclined slide test, both formulations exhibited slow movement, with F11 moving more slowly than F10, but the difference between them was not very large.

Microbial Test

All of the gel formulations submitted for microbiological contamination testing met the predefined sterility criteria. No viable microorganisms were detected in any sample, and each formulation was classified as “pass” according to the standard microbiological acceptance limits.

Drug Content Determination Test

All selected formulations (F5, F10, and F11) exhibited drug contents within acceptable range (Table 19). The mucoadhesive gel (F5) contained 99.5% of the labelled Acyclovir dose.

Table 19: Results of Drug Content Test.

Formulation code		F5	F10	F11
Drug content %	Acyclovir	99.5%	99.8%	99.8%

Stability Study of Optimized Formulation

The evaluation focused on monitoring key physical parameters such as changes in color, odor, clarity, phase separation, and overall appearance (Table 20 to Table 22). After the 3-month period, no noticeable changes in appearance, odor, or pH were observed, confirming the robustness and stability of the formulations.

Table 20: Result of Stability Study for Optimized Batch F5.

Evaluation Parameter	Initial	After 3 Months
Appearance	Bright White; Uniform, Smooth-Glossy Texture	Bright White; Uniform, Smooth-Glossy Texture
Odor	Characteristic Strawberry Aroma	Unchanged Aroma
pH	6.8	6.7

Table 21: Result of Stability Study for Optimized Batch F10.

Evaluation Parameter	Initial	After 3 Months
Appearance	Off-White, Smooth Texture	Off-White, Smooth Texture
Odor	Characteristic Clove Oil Aroma	Unchanged Aroma
pH	6.6	6.35

Table 22: Result of Stability Study for Optimized Batch F11.

Evaluation Parameter	Initial	After 3 Months
Appearance	Off-White, Smooth-Glossy Texture	Off-White, Smooth-Glossy Texture
Odor	Characteristic Clove Oil Aroma	Unchanged Aroma
pH	6.8	6.8

DISCUSSION

The formulated gels exhibited desirable physical properties. All preparations were macroscopically uniform with no phase separation. The optimized Acyclovir gel (F5) was a smooth white gel (with mild strawberry scent), while the optimized gels (F10, F11) were off-white with a characteristic clove odor ideal balance between gel cohesion and muco-adhesion. Formulations F5, F10 and F11 achieved an; lesser formulations (F1–F4, F7) either lacked sufficient viscosity or bio-adhesion. The measured pH of the optimized gels ranged 5.5–6.8, which falls within the physiological range of skin and oral mucosa. Such near-neutral pH minimizes the risk of irritation. Viscosity measurements varied with composition:

weaker gels (e.g. F1) 9.1×10^2 cP, whereas the most viscous (F5) exceeded 1.84×10^4 cP. These values correlate with polymer content, confirming that the formulation variables were tuned to achieve appropriate consistency thick enough to adhere but still spreadable although detailed spreadability data are omitted, the high viscosity in F5, F10, and F11 did not prevent uniform application and was considered suitable for topical dosing.

Biological evaluations demonstrated excellent tolerability. When tested on a group of human volunteers, none of the formulations caused any signs of erythema, skin irritation, or adverse reactions. These findings indicate good biocompatibility of all final gels supporting their safety for topical application.

Microbial contamination tests were performed to ensure the formulations were free from microbial growth or contamination. All tested samples showed no signs of microbial presence, confirming that the products were microbiologically safe.

The quantitative drug content assays showed essentially complete entrapment of the actives. The Acyclovir gel contained 99.5% of its intended drug load, and in F10 and F11 gel were 98.7% and 99.05% respectively. Such high drug content indicates uniform dispersion and minimal loss during manufacturing. This uniformity is critical for dose accuracy and was expected given the thorough mixing steps. Finally, stability testing of the optimized formulations demonstrated robust stability. Over 3 months during the stability study, the appearance, odor, and pH of the formulations remained essentially unchanged. For instance, the acyclovir gel (F5) remained bright white and smooth (pH 6.7-6.8).

CONCLUSION

The optimized oralgel formulation, containing Acyclovir, and clove oil, represents a promising and effective approach for managing oral herpes. It offers antiviral activity, enhanced muco-adhesion, and improved sensory qualities, including taste and texture. The inclusion of a tri-polymer base significantly contributes to the rheological performance and stability of the formulation. These attributes support better patient comfort, compliance, and therapeutic outcomes while minimizing systemic side effects and irritation common in oral drug delivery. It was concluded that the best gel Formulation F5 was found to be optimal viscosity, spreadability, and mucoadhesive strength among the Acyclovir gel formulations NDDS and was flavored with strawberry for enhanced acceptability. Formulation scientist from his experience and knowledge have to significantly in the preformulation study stage

and is an important factor in the NDDS (Novel Drug Delivery Systems) product development process.

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